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Three Narratives of the Ukraine Crisis and the Perspectives of Conflict and Peace Studies

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ABSTRACT

This peace-studies paper addressed the problem of having a mono-source of information from the hegemonic corporate or government owned mainstream media (MSM) for which people only hear one side of the narrative about the Ukraine crisis. This paper responded to the following queries: What are the contending narratives about the Ukraine crisis? From the perspectives of conflict and peace studies, what are the courses of action for conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding? Literature reviewed are drawn from structural analysis, narrative theory, and conflict and peace studies. Qualitative materials from mainstream mass media, alternative media, and social media in both the English and French languages were combed for data analysis which led to the emergence of a grounded theory. I was not able to find alternative voices in Spanish languages news media. The findings included the deliberation of the actions and conflicting narratives among three main players which lead to an impasse: North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) as an international actor as well as Russia and Ukraine as unitary actors in the global scene. From the conflict and peace studies perspectives, this paper recommended the resort to a total halt of warmongering and an intensive process of conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding.

Keywords: Conflict and Peace Studies, NATO, Peace Settlement, Russia, Ukraine

Problem Statement

This article addresses the problematic situation around the world according to which, in most countries, people are bombarded with warmongering narratives mostly from the mainstream media. We only hear one side of the story regarding the conflict surrounding Ukraine, for which reason we support one side of the conflict in a knee-jerk reaction without much critical thinking.

To fill the gap, aside from collecting information about the armed conflict in Ukraine from the mainstream media, this paper shall also conduct research and use other sources of data, including alternative news, social media news, citizenship journalism, and peace journalism. See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Filling the Information Gap

Research Questions

This paper answered these dual queries:

1. What are the contending narratives about the actions related to the Ukraine crisis?
2. From the perspectives of conflict and peace studies, what are the courses of action for conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding?

Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this paper was to investigate and dissect the divergent narratives of NATO, Russia, and Ukraine about the different actions linked to the armed hostilities in Ukraine as well as provide recommendations for conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding with which to end the war in Ukraine.

Contributions of the Study

This article does not only regurgitate the one-sided and clearly biased news and views with which the mainstream media aggressively and constantly bombard us on a massive scale. It likewise searched for and employed alternative news media, citizenship journalism, and peace journalism.

Scope, Limitation, and Delimitation of the Study

The scope of this paper was the Ukraine crisis. It is limited to the actions and perspectives of three major actors in the conflict, namely: NATO, Russia, and Ukraine. This paper does is not pro-NATO, not pro-Russia, and not pro-Ukraine; rather, it is anti-war and pro-peace. It neither prefers nor predicts which party will win the war, as that is outside the scope of this study. See Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Interactions and Narratives of Three Actors and Conflict and Peace Studies Perspectives

The actions and perspectives of the rest of the world are outside the scope of this research. See Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Coverage of the Study

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theory used in this article is narrative theory, according to which despite having a set of facts of a given situation, there are oftentimes various perspectives and interpretations of the same phenomenon (Goodson, 2012). Each person, each party, each official, each leader, or each country can have different understandings of the same event. Thus, we need to listen to and understand each perspective. In this case, the narrative theory indicates that we can heed each voice and match them with a specific happening, in this case the Ukraine crisis. For this paper, the narratives of NATO, Russia, and Ukraine are taken into account with respect to the Ukraine crisis, to which this paper ends with recommendations from the perspectives of conflict and peace studies for conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding. See Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Narratives of the Actions in the Ukraine Crisis

Definition of Terms

Key terms in this paper included conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding. These conceptual keywords are defined here. See Table 1 below:

Table 1: Definition of Terms

Terms	Conceptual Definition
Conflict Resolution	Also known as peacemaking. It includes 1) pacific settlement of conflict (negotiation, enquiry, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, regional office), 2) measures short of war (boycott, embargo, sanctions), and 3) war (United Nations, 1945)
Conflict Transformation	Process of changing from negative actions, relationships, behaviors, and interest to positive ones (Webel & Galtung, 2007)
Peacebuilding	Complex set of long-run actions, policies, programs, structural change at all levels in the aftermath of conflict, including structural peacebuilding, cultural peacebuilding (Ramsbotham, Miall, & Woodhouse, 2016)

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provided an overview of the sources of data for data collection regarding the Ukraine crisis. The three sets of literature include 1) the state and corporate mainstream media, 2) the alternative media, and 3) social media.

In most parts of the world, we hear news from a few interlocking sources, which include state and corporate mainstream media include the usual suspects in mostly western countries: ABC, BBC, CBS, CNN, Le Monde Diplomatique, NBC, New York Times, El País, RFI, RT News, State Department and White House spokespersons, and Washington Post, among others.

Alternative media news sources include that people in western countries but are not aired in the mainstream state or corporate media as well as news from the Global South in Africa, Latin America, in Asia in such countries as China and India, which are not presented in mainstream western media.

Social media news items emanating from citizen journalism are likewise covered in this research. Reporting in social media outlets appear in such platforms as Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, TikTok, Twitter, and the like.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative in nature. It involved employing the Ukraine crisis as a case study. Data collection consisted of the search for online materials. Using the narrative analysis, this paper combed through the whole spectrum of media reports about the Ukraine crisis, including

4th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress government and corporate mainstream media news, alternative media news, and social media news. Data analysis involved coding key terms for the purpose of uncovering themes with which to string together a storyline. The purposive sampling methods utilized included the exploration of major mainstream, alternative, and social media links, after which other links from these key websites were conveniently clicked for further news items about the Ukraine crisis. Materials used in this paper were all culled from publicly available sources; thus, there were neither any human subject nor harm committed to anyone. See Figure 5 below:

Figure 5: Research Methodology

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings section provided answers to the two research questions related to divergent narratives and actions based on conflict and peace studies alternatives.

Findings

This section replied to research question one: What are the contending narratives about the Ukraine crisis? This section presents mapping of the conflict and the contending narratives about the Ukraine crisis. These include the perspectives of NATO, Russia, Ukraine, as well as Conflict and Peace Studies. See Figure 6 below:

Figure 6: Conflict Mapping of the Ukraine Crisis

Contending Narratives. Wars by definition are violent (Tilly, 2003). The basic principle in conflict and peace studies include, among others, to listen to all sides, not to take sides, to call for a stop to violence, and an appeal to work towards a peace settlement, after which the parties to the conflict start conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding.(Barash & Webel, 2009).

There are multiple perspectives about the conflict in Ukraine. Based on a review of the news sources, these three divergent sources of news talk past each other. First, mainstream media sources are mostly warmongering, blaming the other side. Mainstream media in NATO portray Zelenskyy as Churchill and hero and pain Putin as Hitler and the megalomaniac villain, indicating that Ukraine is winning the war (Bet-David, 2022).

Second, alternative media and news sources are either warmongering but claiming one’s own country is at fault or are engaged in peace journalism, calling for an end to the war. For these two reasons, these alternative voices are not heard in the mainstream. Alternative sources reveal that NATO broke its promise of non-expansion and encircle Russia, which solicited the wrath of Russia (Sison, 2022).

Third, social media is a venue in which citizen journalism is exercised. For instance, people who personally experience living in Ukraine, covering the news in Ukraine about Ukraine but not covered by mainstream media, or volunteers who went to Ukraine to help in humanitarian or war efforts upload their personal accounts of what they witness. To be clear, witnesses who returned from Ukraine have videos to show that both sides—the Ukrainian Azov battalion and the Russian military—have committed war crimes (Bocquet, 2022). Note, however, in all media—mainstream, alternative, and citizen journalism—both factual news and fake news have the same likelihood of appearing.

The spokespersons of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of both China and India are now speaking openly about being coerced to take sides in the Ukraine crisis and to impose economic sanctions on Russia, but they assert non-alignment and criticize NATO as the cause of the war.

On the one hand, the mainstream media news in NATO and Ukraine portrays Russia as the antagonist, while the mainstream media in Russia depict NATO and Ukraine as the antagonist. On

4th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress
 the other hand, the alternative media news in NATO shows that NATO is the villain. There is no alternative media news in Ukraine and Russia. Zelensky shut down all TV and news media outlets, keeping only one centralized source of news. There is no alternative news in Russia. See Figure 7 below:

Figure 7: Three Major Types of Sources of Literature about the Ukraine Crisis

Conflict and Peace Studies Perspectives. This section responded to the second research question: What are the conflict and peace studies perspectives of the Ukraine crisis? If on the one hand, the three main actors are promoting war, there are actors who are anti-war and clamor for alternatives for the attainment of peace in Ukraine. Ukrainian (Sheliashenko, 2022) and non-Ukrainian scholars and activists have presented peace and anti-war actions as alternatives to the warmongering. This paper is written from the perspectives of conflict and peace studies, as a result of which it does not assert whether NATO, Ukraine, or Russia must win this war. The episode of the conflict is the Russian invasion of also called the “special military operation” in Ukraine. The epicenter of the conflict is NATO pushing eastward to the border of Russia.

This research is prescriptive, suggesting ways by which the war could end. Through conflict resolution or peacemaking, parties to the conflict stop the armed hostilities at once and enter into a serious peace settlement, which entails conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding. There are many ways by which conflict resolution could be achieved, including either direct negotiations among the parties or mediation through an outside neutral party (United Nations, 1945). In negotiation, peacemaking or conflict resolution requires the direct participation of top-level actors to the conflict. In the case of negotiation, top representatives of Ukraine and Russia meet directly and discuss the terms of their peace accord. In mediation, it involves an external, party that will be neutral to the conflict and ensure that compromises will be made with a view to achieving a peace deal. In the case of mediation, top-level political representatives of Russia and Ukraine need to have the active but neutral participation of an external party to the conflict which will ensure both sides listen to each other and come to an acceptable agreement on both sides.

By conflict transformation is meant the creation of constructive change processes which mitigate violence, augment justice in social systems and relationships as well as to deal with relationship issues (Lederach, 2003, p.14). A transformative vision requires considering the conflict as giving an opportunity for constructive growth as well as the willingness to respond positively (Lederach, 2003). Conflict transformation addresses the interpersonal, social, cultural, and structural patterns,

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 content, context, and structure of relationships between the Russians and the Ukrainians across the border.

Peacebuilding involves implementing programs to address the root causes of the conflict to ensure sustainable and just peace from the time after which a peace settlement is signed. These post-conflict peacebuilding long-term efforts cuts across all levels of the affected societies. These peacebuilding efforts include, among others, relief, rehabilitation, grassroots efforts, conflict resolution training, and building top-level inter-state harmonious relationships (Lederach, 1997). For conflict resolution, conflict transformation, and peacebuilding to work, all parties to the conflict at all levels of society must be on board. See Figure 8 below:

Figure 8: Approaches to Peacebuilding in the Ukraine Crisis

Discussion

All actors in the conflict—namely NATO, Ukraine, and Russia—are arming to the teeth, prolonging the war, rather than ending it. There is widespread Russophobia in pro-NATO news. Anyone who is pro-peace or anti-war is automatically labeled wrongly as pro-Putin. The war in Ukraine is a proxy war between the hegemon and Russia (Géopolitique, 2022). If we leave NATO to run its course, Europe and the west are marching towards war (Guaino, 2022). Intermediaries and peacemakers (MacGinty & Wanis-St. John, 2022) can help transform the war escalation to conflict resolution (Kriesberg, 2006). A neutral third-party must take up the cudgel for the worthy cause of brokering a peace settlement between the warring parties in order to end and transform the war (Ury, 2000). Compromises on all sides have to be made that are acceptable to all parties (Fisher, Ury, & Patton, 1991).

Some issues must be settled. One is NATO membership vis-à-vis neutrality. Two is the discrimination and attacks on Russian speaking population in eastern Ukraine in violation of the Minsk agreements (Hill TV, 2022b).. Three is the question of Nazis and other anti-Russian ultra-nationalists. Despite NATO denying the active role of the Azov battalion, many Ukrainian civilians, after leaving, have attested first-hand to news media that Azov use them as human shields and does not allow them to leave the Azovstal steel plant (France 24, 2022). Four is the issue of biolabs (Hill TV, 2022a).

The war in Ukraine is a failure of leadership at all levels: failure of the hegemon, the Ukrainian leadership, and the Russian leadership (Ishchenko, 2022). However, there are some dissenting

4th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress voices. Angela Merkel, for example, stated that the two sides of the Atlantic do not speak with one common interest in mind, emphasizing that she speaks for the interest of Germany.

Not given air time in mainstream media are anti-war politicians on both sides of the Atlantic. They call for the cessation of hostilities and a stop to sending weapons, volunteers, mercenaries, and money for the war efforts of Ukraine. They span the left-to-right political spectrum.

These anti-war politicians include Richard Boyd Barrett (Irish Member of Parliament), Clare Daly (Irish Member of European Parliament), Tulsi Gabbard (Democrat), George Galloway (Workers Party of Britain), and Rand Paul (Republican). For being anti-war, they risk being incorrectly labeled as pro-Putin and pro-Russia. Clearly, this name calling is reminiscent of the red-baiting and red-tagging during the Cold War. Thus, we are now living under Cold War 2.0.

There are two options for the future of the Ukraine crisis: 1) war of attrition or 2) end of war. The Russian military analysis V. Litovkin stressed that in the event that NATO sends troops to Ukraine, that is tantamount to an all-out war, stressing that Russia has nuclear arms that could destroy NATO countries (MEMRI, 2022). See Figure 9 below:

Figure 9: Two Alternative Futures for Ukraine

In a snapshot, the paper is encapsulated in the following Figure 9 below:

Figure 9: Summary of the Ukraine Crisis

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

In a nutshell, there are two possible outcomes on opposite ends to this conflict in Ukraine: continuing war or peace. Following the current dominant logic of NATO, Russia, and Ukraine, war will be the way forward, leading to continuing waste of resources for the purchase of military hardware, more suffering to human beings and destruction to property. Powerful politicians and the military-industrial complex benefit from violence and war (Nordstrom, 2008).

The other way forward is to seek peace and to follow it. War is now omnipresent, but we have the potential for peace now as well (Fry, 2007). Peace scholars and activists have been calling for the cessation of the armed hostilities and for the inking of an agreement, as wars end with peace settlements. See Figure 10 below:

Figure 10: Decision Tree of the Road Ahead for Ukraine

Policy Recommendations

4th International CEO Communication, Economics, Organization & Social Sciences Congress

Written from the perspective of conflict and peace studies, this article recommends the warring parties to cease armed hostilities immediately and engage in constructive peace settlement through negotiation or mediation, after which they work towards conflict transformation and long-term peacebuilding.

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